

A 2D graphene-manganese oxide nanosheet hybrid synthesized by a single step liquid-phase co-exfoliation method for supercapacitor applications

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Abstract

The exfoliation of bulk-layered materials into 2D-nanosheets dramatically enhances their surface area and opens up novel properties. The exploitation of these advantageous properties for use in energy storage is, however, conditioned by the effective utilization of the available surface area and the effective combination of 2D-nanosheets holding complementary properties. In this work, a 2D graphene-manganese oxide nanosheet hybrid, in which graphene was interleaved between manganese oxide nanosheets, was synthesized following a novel single-step liquid-phase co-exfoliation method. This active material was used to manufacture supercapacitor electrodes using a scalable spray deposition method. The interleaving of graphene between manganese oxide nanosheets enabled a better use of the pseudocapacitive properties of the manganese oxide nanosheets (the hybrid was tested in a 0.5 M K₂SO₄ aqueous electrolyte) achieving a geometric capacitance of 80 mF cm⁻² (single electrode), volumetric capacitances of 300 F cm⁻³ (single electrode) and 40.9 F cm⁻³ (symmetric device), and volumetric energy and power of 5.5 mWh cm⁻³ and 2,193.1 mW cm⁻³ (symmetric device), respectively. This performance is promising in the context of micro-supercapacitor applications, where performance per unit area and per unit volume are relevant for miniaturization. This work demonstrates the remarkable versatility of liquid-phase exfoliation to synthesize hybrids with tailored properties providing the proof-of-concept work for further investigation and exploitation of 2D hybrids for supercapacitor applications.

1. Introduction

Electrochemical capacitors (ECs), also known as supercapacitors, are energy storage devices with a high power density and a high degree of cyclability. Based on their energy storage mechanism, ECs can be classified as electrical double layer capacitors (EDLCs) and pseudocapacitors. Electrical double layer capacitors store energy electrostatically at the electrode-electrolyte interface whereas pseudocapacitors use

reversible, and fast faradaic processes occurring at the surface of electroactive materials. High surface area carbon-based materials are typically used for EDLCs whereas several transition metal oxides with faradaic activity have been investigated as pseudocapacitors. Ruthenium oxide is the metal oxide with the highest capacitance reported thus far; however, due to its high cost and toxicity, alternative low-cost and environmentally friendly transition metal oxides are being investigated.

As first reported by Lee and Goodenough in 1999, manganese oxide is a material that exhibits pseudocapacitive properties [1] with a high theoretical capacitance of 1,380 F g⁻¹ [2]. The energy storage mechanisms proposed for MnO₂ are: (1) reversible oxidation-reduction processes, (2) cation adsorption-desorption, and (3) ion-intercalation [3,4]. The first two mechanisms occur at the surface of the electroactive materials and therefore the achievement of a high surface area is key for maximization of energy density. High electrochemical utilization and capacitances reaching the theoretical values have been achieved by depositing thin films (10-100 nm) of MnO₂ directly onto the current collectors, which shortens the paths for electron and ion transport [2,5]. Moreover, a strategy to enhance both energy density and electrochemical utilization, has been the deposition of thin films onto electrochemically active current collectors, which are typically high surface area, porous carbon materials that combine high electrical conductivity and double layer capacitance properties. MnO₂ has been deposited onto carbon nanotubes [6–8,5], mesoporous carbon [9], carbon nanofoams [10], and more recently graphene-like materials [11–14]. Graphene is a 2D nanomaterial with high electrical conductivity and a high theoretical surface area of 2,600 m² g⁻¹ [15–19] which makes it an ideal electronically conductive scaffold for pseudocapacitive materials.

Most of the previous work combining MnO₂ and graphene for supercapacitors applications used graphene oxide derived graphene (GOG) [11–14]. However, the use of GOG has several shortcomings. First, unlike liquid-phase exfoliated graphene, GOG is a material with a high fraction of structural defects that undermines its electronic conductivity (100 S m⁻¹ [20,21]) [22–24]. While the defective-nature of GOG may improve electrolyte access into the electrode, its electrical conductivity is rather poor resulting in the need for adding electrically conductive additives [13]. Electrically conductive additives (typically acetylene black) and polymeric binders - mixed with electrochemically active materials in electrodes to maintain mechanical stability [12–14] -, add up to the non-active mass fraction of the electrode which results in a concomitant reduction of gravimetric capacitance. Second, the synthesis of GOG is a multi-step, time-consuming and non-cost effective approach that requires the use of toxic reducing agents. Defect-free graphene with

high electrical conductivity has been produced by chemical vapor deposition (CVD) methods; however this procedure does not offer scope for scalability [25]. In our previous work, we demonstrated a cost-effective and scalable method to produce defect-free and mostly monolayer/few layers graphene by surfactant-aided exfoliation in aqueous media that was subsequently processed by spray deposition in order to manufacture graphene thin films with a high electrical conductivity of $4,905 \text{ S m}^{-1}$ [26,27].

In this work, we present a novel and facile method to produce a construct in which 2D MnO_2 nanosheets and graphene are interleaved with each other in a single step liquid-phase co-exfoliation synthesis. The co-exfoliation method consists of the simultaneous exfoliation of manganese oxide and graphite in a single solvent and involves some physico-chemical processes [32]. Unlike procedures followed in previous reports, the interleaving of graphene and 2D MnO_2 nanosheets was achieved without the need of chemical functionalization of a graphene-like material [13]. The graphene- MnO_2 “hybrid” combines the high electrical conductivity properties of defect-free graphene with the pseudocapacitive properties of 2D MnO_2 nanosheets. The graphene nanosheets act as localized current collector of 2D MnO_2 nanosheets enabling an enhanced electrochemical utilization of MnO_2 . Binder-free supercapacitor electrodes were manufactured using a scalable spray-deposition method. The thickness of electrodes, ranging from 20 nm to 11 μm , was increased up to a threshold (critical thickness) where no further charge storage was achieved ensuring that all of the electrode material was effectively utilized. The critical thickness was considered a metric of performance of the electrochemically active material, the larger the critical thickness, the better the electrochemical utilization of the material. The graphene- MnO_2 hybrid displayed high electrochemical utilization achieving a geometric capacitance of 80 mF cm^{-2} at a critical thickness of 9.7 μm . This capacitance was much higher than what was found for electrodes made solely of manganese oxide nanosheets (27.5 mF cm^{-2} at a critical thickness of 3.4 μm). Moreover, the graphene- MnO_2 hybrid achieved a high volumetric capacitance of 300 F cm^{-3} as a single electrode and 40.9 F cm^{-3} as symmetric device. A symmetric device exhibited maximum energy and power per unit volume of 5.5 mWh cm^{-3} and $2,193.1 \text{ mW cm}^{-3}$. This performance is competitive with the performance of other 2D pseudocapacitive materials and offers potential for thin-film based micro-supercapacitor applications.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Materials

Manganese nitrate tetrahydrate ($\text{Mn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, purity $\geq 97.0\%$), graphite flakes, potassium permanganate (KMnO_4 , BioUltra $\geq 99.0\%$), poly(ethylene glycol)-block-poly(propylene glycol)-block-poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG-PPG-PEG, average $M_w = 5800 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$), and isopropanol (99.9 %) were supplied by Sigma Aldrich; Poly(ethyleneimine) (PEI, $M_w = 70,000$) by Alfa-Aesar. Deionised water (DI-water, $10 \text{ M} \cdot \text{cm}$) was used for all the synthesis protocols.

2.2. Synthesis of manganese oxide flower-like nanostructures (MOFN)

Manganese oxide was synthesized following the method described by Hao J. *et al* [28]. $\text{Mn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1.67 g, 6.66 mmol) was dissolved in DI-water (100 ml), and then the triblock copolymer PEG-PPG-PEG (0.5 g) was added. A second aqueous solution of KMnO_4 (0.1 M, 100 ml) was prepared. The first solution was heated up and maintained at a 45°C temperature using a hot plate and it was kept under vigorous stirring while the second solution was added drop-by-drop. The obtained brownish precipitate was washed thoroughly, first with DI-water and then with ethanol; it was then vacuum filtrated and dried in an oven at 50°C overnight.

2.3. Liquid-phase exfoliation of manganese oxide nanosheets (MON) and partially exfoliated manganese oxide (PEMO) in suspension

The MOFN synthesized as described above (300 mg) was added to isopropanol (30 ml). The dispersion was processed in an ultrasonic bath (60 % power, 37 kHz) for 3 hours, followed by centrifugation (5000 rpm (RCF = 4695, 3 hours) and collection of the supernatant (top 70 % volume). PEMO was synthesized following a similar procedure with the exception of the centrifugation step (1500 rpm (RCF = 1690), 30 min).

2.4. Liquid-phase co-exfoliation of graphite and manganese oxide to produce a graphene-manganese oxide nanosheet hybrid (GMOH) in suspension

The MOFN synthesized as described above (300 mg) and as-purchased graphite flakes (300 mg) were added to isopropanol (30 ml). The mix was processed in an ultrasonic bath (60 % power, 37 kHz) for 9 hours, followed by centrifugation (5000 rpm (RCF = 4695), 3 hours) and collection of the supernatant (top 70 %).

2.5. Electrode manufacture

Electrodes with an area of 1 cm² were manufactured by spray-deposition of suspensions of active materials onto indium tin oxide (ITO) coated glass substrates (7 / sq sheet resistance) using an ultrasonic spray deposition equipment (USI Prism Ultracoat 300). The spray-deposition method has been described in our previous work [29,30] and some details are described in the electronic supplementary information (ESI).

2.6. Electrochemical characterization

Electrodes of MON, PEMO and GMOH were tested in a half-cell configuration using an Ag/AgCl reference electrode and a platinum coil as counter electrode. Symmetric supercapacitors were assembled using two GMOH electrodes. The electrolyte used for all testing was 0.5 M K₂SO₄. The tests were done in a Reference 600/EIS300 Gamry potentiostat/galvanostat. Cyclic voltammetry experiments were performed in a potential range of 0 to 1 V versus Ag/AgCl. Galvanostatic charge-discharge experiments were performed in a potential range 0 to 1 V vs Ag/AgCl. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurements were performed using a AC voltage of 5 mV rms in a frequency range of 0.001 Hz to 2 MHz. Equipment and characterization techniques are detailed in the ESI.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Material characterization

Compared with crystalline manganese oxide, higher pseudocapacitances have been achieved by amorphous manganese oxide where fast proton and ion transport for charge storage are favored [7]. Here, a poorly crystalline material was synthesized following a typical co-precipitation synthetic method [28,31]. As shown in Figures 1a-1c, the as-synthesized material had a characteristic flower-like and mesoporous morphology with protruding petal-like nanostructures. Hence, the material is called manganese oxide flower-like nanostructures (MOFN). The low intensity and high degree of Scherrer broadening - due to a small crystal size of the peaks in the XRD diffraction pattern for MOFN shown in Figure 2 is a signature of the poor crystallinity of the as-synthesized MOFN. Pattern matching structure refinements were performed in an attempt to identify the present phase(s). Five possible phases were considered: α -MnO₂·3H₂O (JCPDS 00-044-0140), K_{2-x}Mn₈O₁₆ (ICDS 00-044-1386), ramsdellite-type MnO₂ (JCPDS 00-039-0375 and JCPDS-00-042-1316), and birnessite-type K_{0.5}Mn₂O₄·1.5H₂O (JCPDS-00-042-1317).

Figure 1 - Micrographs of (a) MOFN (HIM); (b)-(c) close up of MOFN showing the presence of petal-like nanostructures (TEM); (d) PEMO (TEM); (e)-(f) MON (TEM); and (g)-(h) GMOH (TEM).

Figure 2 - XRD patterns of MOFN, PEMO and MON.

As shown in Figure S2a, the refinement resulted in a poor fitting for most of the proposed phases, especially for $2\theta < 30^\circ$ where the background signal became important, partially obscuring the contribution from the “crystalline” phase. A best fit was observed for birnessite-type $K_{0.5}Mn_2O_4 \cdot 1.5H_2O$ (JCPDS-00-042-1317), although still poor for the $15^\circ < 2\theta < 25^\circ$ range. Therefore, the MOFN crystal phase could be likely identified as birnessite - a definitive phase identification requires a better fit which in turn requires better quality of the experimental data. Thermogravimetric analysis (see ESI) showed a weight loss due to water which supports the presence of a hydrated compound.

Upon liquid-phase exfoliation in isopropanol (IPA), and as described in the experimental section, the petal-like nanostructures of MOFN (Figures 1c) gave place to manganese oxide nanosheets (MON) (Figures 1e and 1f) and partially exfoliated manganese oxide (PEMO) (Figure 1d) in suspension. Tuning the centrifugation rates allowed the

isolation of MON and PEMO in separate suspensions. The typical dimensions of MON were 20 - 40 nm and thickness of 3.2 ± 1.2 nm [32]. Figure 2 shows the XRD spectra of MON and PEMO. Pattern matching structure refinements were performed considering the same crystal phases as for MOFN. The pattern matching refinement in Figure S2b shows a good fit of the MON data to the birnessite-type $K_{0.5}Mn_2O_4 \cdot 1.5H_2O$ (JCPDS-00-042-1317). Similar to the case of MOFN, the fit was poor in the $15^\circ < 2\theta < 25^\circ$ range. In the case of PEMO, shown in Figure S2c, the fit to all the phases was poor. According to the discussion above, the MON phase could be likely assigned to birnessite and in the case of PEMO, no definitive phase identification can be done.

Next, graphite and MOFN were simultaneously co-exfoliated in IPA resulting in a graphene-manganese oxide nanosheet hybrid (GMOH) suspension of $0.3-0.5 \text{ mg ml}^{-1}$ concentration. The GMOH suspension was stable against re-aggregation for at least six months. As shown in the TEM images in Figures 1g-1h, the MON were typically lying on top of graphene. The typical dimensions of graphene were 400 nm lateral size and 6.5 ± 2.4 nm (few layers graphene) [32]. Figure S1 (ESI) shows a diffraction pattern of a graphene flake underlying a MON. This diffraction pattern shows the typical sixfold symmetry of graphene [33,26]. Further details regarding the co-exfoliation process and morphology of MON and GMOH are given in a separate work recently published [32].

Next, thin films deposited onto ITO-coated glass (electrodes) or silicon substrates were manufactured by a scalable spray-deposition method and used for material characterization and electrochemical characterization, respectively. Upon spray deposition of GMOH, the inter-leaving of graphene and MON was achieved.

Figure 3 - Raman spectra of graphene, MON and GMOH. Numeric labels identify peak position (cm^{-1}) and text labels identify characteristic bands of graphene.

Raman spectroscopy (RS) was used to confirm the simultaneous presence of graphene and MON in the GMOH spray-deposited thin films. Figure 3 shows the Raman

spectra of MON, GMOH and graphene samples. The spectrum of the graphene sample showed the characteristic bands identifying graphene: the G band at 1345.9 cm^{-1} , the D band at 1563.7 cm^{-1} and the 2D band at 2681.2 cm^{-1} [33,26]. The GMOH sample showed similar bands confirming the presence of graphene: the G band at 1352.6 cm^{-1} , the D band at 1580.4 cm^{-1} and the 2D band at 2702.3 cm^{-1} . The spectra of MON and GMOH were very similar in the 50 cm^{-1} to 1000 cm^{-1} spectral range: MON showed a peak at 629.2 cm^{-1} and a broad peak at about 296.2 cm^{-1} , which were also present in GMOH at 655.6 cm^{-1} and 335.4 cm^{-1} . This confirms that GMOH effectively incorporated both exfoliated graphene and MON species. These findings were supported by TGA characterization (see Figure S3 at ESI).

The phase identification of the crystal phase of MON and the MON component in GMOH using Raman was uncertain. It is well known that laser-induced heating leads to degradation of manganese oxides giving place to new phases including Mn_2O_3 and Mn_3O_4 [34,35]. It is possible that the samples here analyzed underwent this type of degradation and that the peak at 655.6 cm^{-1} may describe the presence of Mn_3O_4 , previously reported to appear at 650 cm^{-1} [34].

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) of MOFN, MON, graphene and GMOH was performed to confirm the presence of graphene and MON in the GMOH and to quantify their proportions. The as-acquired TGA curves and corresponding TGA derivative curves are shown in Figure S3 (ESI) where a full analysis is addressed. The TGA curve of GMOH showed weight losses of 18.5 %, 15.5 %, and 1.75 % attributed to water evaporation, graphene degradation, and oxygen removal due to the transformation of MnO_2 to Mn_2O_3 , respectively. On this basis, the ratio of graphene/manganese oxide in GMOH was calculated to be 19 %/ 81 %.

The surface area of MOFN, MON and GMOH were studied by analysis of the nitrogen adsorption isotherms using the Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) method. As shown in Figure S4 (ESI), all the adsorption-desorption isotherms were type IV [36]. The measured surface areas were $124.9\text{ m}^2\text{ g}^{-1}$ (MON), $138.9\text{ m}^2\text{ g}^{-1}$ (GMOH) and $121.9\text{ m}^2\text{ g}^{-1}$ (MOFN). Due to their 2D nature, MON and GMOH must have a much higher surface area than here measured. Unfortunately, 2D nanomaterials have a natural tendency to re-aggregate after removal of any media (solvent) separating the individual nanosheets - the samples for surface area measurements consisted of powders prepared by vacuum filtration. Aggregation of 2D nanomaterials during device fabrication is a disadvantageous condition for energy storage applications. Further material and electrode design is necessary to solve this problem.

4. Electrochemical characterization

4.1. Analysis background

The end applications of supercapacitors have different performance requirements which in turn dictate the suitable device dimensions (electrode thickness, electrode footprint and total volume) and weight. Applications in the large-range sector (industrial cranes, transportation, load-leveling) require high energy density, and thus, electrodes with thicknesses in the millimetre range contribute to fulfill this requirement. In the case of micro-supercapacitors, defined as miniaturized supercapacitors to be utilized as power sources or energy storage units in micro-electronics [37], the electrode thickness required for miniaturization and enhancement of capacitance, energy and power per unit volume is in the nano- to micro-metre scale ($< 10 \text{ m}$) [37]. It is important to bear in mind that electrochemical utilization and coulombic efficiency are critically affected by electrode thickness. Maximum electrochemical utilization is achieved by electrodes with thicknesses in the nanometre range resulting in a large gravimetric capacitance. However, capacitance, energy and power per unit mass do not scale up with electrode thickness [2].

The dimensions/weight of the supercapacitor electrodes relative to the overall dimensions/weight of the device dictate the suitable metrics to evaluate their performance [37]. For large-range supercapacitors, the weight of electrodes accounts for a large fraction of the total mass of the device. In this case, while evaluating electrode performance per unit mass is meaningful. In the case of micro-supercapacitors, the mass of nano- to micro-metre thick electrodes is negligible as compared to the total mass of the device and therefore gravimetric measurements are inappropriate [37]. Because the volume and electrode footprint of the device are key design elements in micro-supercapacitors, the determination of capacitance, energy and power per unit area and volume is suitable [37].

Herein, the charge storage properties of MON, GMOH and PEMO were investigated by several electrochemical techniques. Because the envisaged application of the electrodes manufactured in this study is for micro-supercapacitors, we evaluated performance per unit area (geometric area) and per unit volume. For the sake of comparison with previous reports in the literature, the performance was also evaluated per unit mass especially in the case of the GMOH symmetric device.

4.2. Capacitance as a function of electrode thickness

First, the capacitance of PEMO, MON and GMOH was evaluated as a function of the electrode thickness (20 nm to 30 m) using cyclic voltammetry (at 5 mV s^{-1} scan rate, 1 V electrochemical window, half cell configuration). The aim was to determine the limiting

thickness of an electrode holding solely active material that effectively contributes to charge storage. This approach enabled: (1) an evaluation of the electrochemical utilization, (2) an objective evaluation of geometric and volumetric capacitance (a function of electrode thickness), and (3) an objective comparison across electrodes of different thicknesses and different materials (PEMO, MON and GMOH).

Figure 4 - (a) Capacitance per unit geometric area (1 cm²) and (b) capacitance per unit volume as a function of electrode thickness for MON, GMOH and PEMO electrodes. The inset in (a) shows data for MON at a suitable scale. The solid lines in (a) are linear fittings (R² = 0.99). The dotted lines in (b) were added as guidelines. The arrows indicate critical thicknesses. The capacitance was determined by analysis of cyclic voltammetry at a scan rate of 5 mV s⁻¹.

Figure 4a shows that the geometric capacitance for MON, GMOH and PEMO increased following an approximate linear trend, reaching a maximum at a critical thickness t_c , approximately plateauing at larger thicknesses, and eventually decreasing. The final decrease of capacitance may be ascribed to an electrode packing effect that prevents electrolyte access. This effect is very likely produced by a noticeable degree of nanosheet aggregation as the electrode thickness goes beyond the critical thickness. The critical thickness t_c was considered a suitable metric for evaluating electrochemical utilization: the larger the t_c is, the larger is the quantity of material effectively utilized for charge storage. Following this evaluation criterion, the best electrochemical utilization was achieved by GMOH with a maximum capacitance of 80.0 mF cm⁻² at $t_c = 9,700$ nm; PEMO had a slightly lower maximum geometric capacitance of 73 mF cm⁻² with similar electrochemical utilization, $t_c = 10,738$ nm; and MON had the lowest maximum geometric capacitance of 27.5 mF cm⁻² with the lowest electrochemical utilization, $t_c =$ of 3,376 nm. It is worth noticing that the GMOH electrodes showed larger geometric capacitances than PEMO and MON at all thicknesses. Figure 4b shows that high volumetric capacitances were achieved by exfoliated 2D nanomaterials-based electrodes with the minimum thickness (t_m): 473 F cm⁻³ at $t_m = 55$ nm for MON and 300 F cm⁻³ at $t_m = 69$ nm for GMOH. A lower volumetric capacitance was found for the partially exfoliated manganese oxide PEMO: 244 F cm⁻³ at $t_m = 77$ nm. For critical thicknesses t_c , considerable volumetric capacitances were still

maintained: 81.5 F cm⁻³ at $t_c = 3,376$ nm for MON, 82.5 F cm⁻³ at $t_c = 9,701$ nm for GMOH, and 68 F cm⁻³ at $t_c = 10,737$ nm for PEMO. All the capacitance values per unit area and per unit volume at t_c and t_m are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1 - Maximum geometric and volumetric capacitances for MON, GMOH and PEMO electrodes. Critical and minimum electrode thicknesses are named t_c and t_m respectively.

Material	t_c (nm)	Maximum capacitance per area (mF cm⁻²)	Capacitance per volume at t_c (F cm⁻³)
MON	3,376	27.5	81.5
GMOH	9,701	80	82.5
PEMO	10,737	73	68
Material	t_m (nm)	Capacitance per area at t_m (mF cm⁻²)	Maximum capacitance per volume (F cm⁻³)
MON	55	2.60	473
GMOH	69	2.0	300
PEMO	77	1.9	244

MON exhibited the lowest geometric capacitance and the lowest critical thickness. Both conditions are correlated with a poorer electrochemical performance. This result can be attributed to several factors including: (1) re-aggregation and re-stacking of the exfoliated 2D-nanosheets upon deposition which has the ultimate effect of reducing the surface area available for charge storage, (2) the lack of an electrically conductive additive and (3) the lack of porosity preventing electrolyte access. In the case of PEMO, a larger capacitance was achieved due to the inherent mesoporosity of the partially exfoliated “nano-flowers” which resulted in a higher surface area available for charge storage. In GMOH, the interleaved graphene provided electrical conductivity between the MnO₂ nanosheets enabling an enhanced electrochemical utilization of the MnO₂ nanosheets, otherwise poorly contributing to pseudocapacitance due to their semiconducting nature. As in the case of MON, GMOH also exhibited aggregation, a problem that was not addressed in this work.

4.3. Evaluation of the performance of MON, GMOH and PEMO electrodes

A second step in the evaluation of the charge storage properties of MON, GMOH and PEMO was the study of thin and thick electrodes in a half-cell configuration. Based on the previous analysis of the capacitance as a function of thickness (Figure 4), it was considered

that thick electrodes were those with thicknesses = t_c , and thin electrodes were those with thicknesses < 1000 nm. In the case of MON, thick electrodes of $t_c \approx 3000$ nm were manufactured. In order to compare the performance across electrochemically active materials MON, GMOH and PEMO, electrodes of similar thicknesses $\approx 3,000$ nm were also manufactured for GMOH and PEMO. The control of thickness of spray-deposited films in the nanometer scale is more challenging due to differences in concentration of suspensions of the different active materials. Therefore, thin electrodes of only comparable but not similar thickness were manufactured: MON (about 100 nm), GMOH, (about 250 nm) and PEMO (about 832 nm). Due to this limitation of accurate control of electrode thicknesses, the electrochemical properties were calculated per unit volume.

Representative cyclic voltammograms (CVs) of thin electrodes of all the materials are shown in Figures 5a. All CVs displayed a rectangular-like shape typical of pseudocapacitive activity and attributed to the exchange of protons and cations typical of amorphous manganese dioxide [38,7,39]:

Figure 5 - Charge storage properties of MON, GMOH and PEMO electrodes: (a) representative cyclic voltammograms for thin electrodes at a scan rate of 5 mV s^{-1} , (b) capacitance per unit volume as function of scan rate for both thin and thick electrodes.

The CVs displayed redox waves associated with the transition of interfacial oxyanions of various oxidation states including Mn(3+)/Mn(2+), Mn(4+)/Mn(3+) and Mn(6+)/Mn(4+) [38,40,41,2].

Figure 5b shows the capacitance determined by cyclic voltammetry as a function of the scan rate (5 to 700 mV s^{-1}) per unit volume for thin and thick electrodes of MON, GMOH and PEMO. The GMOH electrodes had the largest capacitances at all scan rates reaching values of 300 F cm^{-3} (thickness of 224 nm), in agreement with the data in Figure 4. As it is typical of pseudocapacitive materials, the overall capacitance decreased with scan rate following an exponential decay reflecting the limitations imposed by the kinetics of the

pseudocapacitive processes described above. Nevertheless, the GMOH electrodes had a capacitance retention of 57.2 % at 200 mV s⁻¹ and 42.8 % at the high scan rate of 700 mV s⁻¹ (Table 2).

Table 2 - Capacitance retention of thin and thick electrodes of MON, GMOH and PEMO as determined by cyclic voltammetry.

Scan Rate	Thickness (nm)	Capacitance Retention (%)	
		200 mV s ⁻¹	700 mV s ⁻¹
MON	111	45.6	32.5
GMOH	224	57.2	42.8
PEMO	786	50.0	33.6
MON	3700	12.8	4.5
GMOH	3211	43.5	16.8
PEMO	3195	38.1	13.4

The capacitance per unit mass of a GMOH electrode (304 nm thickness) was 217 F g⁻¹, as determined from charge-discharge experiments at a discharge current of 250 mA g⁻¹. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) studies of the thick MON, GMOH and PEMO electrodes were performed. As shown in Figure S5a, all the electrodes showed a deviation from the ideal capacitive behaviour (a constant Z real while -Z imaginary decreases, a phase angle of -90°, and a frequency-|Z| plot with a slope of -1) and this effect was more pronounced for the MON and PEMO electrodes. Deviation from the ideal capacitive behaviour of pseudocapacitive electrodes has been reported to be due to the faradaic activity of active materials [42]. In this work a deviation from the ideal capacitive behaviour was attributed to the faradaic activity of the manganese oxide nanosheets.

It is evident from Figure S5 that the EIS spectra of the GMOH electrodes are substantially different from those of the MON and PEMO electrodes. As shown in Figure S5b, unlike MON and PEMO electrodes, the GMOH electrode developed a high frequency loop. Figures S5c and S5d show that GMOH exhibited a switch (going from high to low frequencies) towards an approximate capacitive behaviour (phase angle of -90 °, and frequency-|Z| plot with a slope of -1), whereas this transition was not observed for MON and PEMO electrodes.

The EIS spectra were fitted to the equivalent electrical circuits (EECs) described in Figure S6 (ESI). Due to their different EIS behaviour, model 1 was used for the GMOH electrode and model 2 for the MON and PEMO electrodes. In model 1, the R2CPE1 circuit describes the high frequency response of the GMOH electrode at the current collector-

electrode interface [43], whereas the CPE2 describes the inhomogeneous capacitance of the GMOH electrode at medium-low frequencies. In model 2, the CPE1(R2Wo1) circuit describes a distributed impedance of the MON and PEMO electrodes at all frequencies. The results of the fitting are summarized in Tables S1 and S2. Notice the small charge transfer resistance $R_2 = 4.2\Omega$ of the GMOH electrode whereas the equivalent for the MON (95.0Ω) and PEMO (118.4Ω) were an order of magnitude higher. This was attributed to the presence of electrically conducting graphene in the GMOH electrode.

Since the determined values of α_{CPE} for the fitting of all electrodes were 0.82-0.84, we cannot claim capacitance values from the EEC modeling. However, as an approximation, the capacitance of the GMOH electrode was $T_{CPE2} = 14\text{ mF cm}^{-2}$ (for an $\alpha_{CPE2} = 0.85$), which is in the range of values determined using cyclic voltammetry.

According to the model proposed by P.L. Taberna *et al.*, the capacitance of a supercapacitor can be calculated using Equation S6 at all frequencies, and the so-determined capacitance at the lowest frequency corresponds to the capacitance determined by galvanostatic charge-discharge measurements [44]. Figure S5e shows the capacitance of our electrodes using this approach and Table S3 summarizes the capacitance values at the lowest frequency. These values were comparable to those determined using cyclic voltammetry (shown in Figure 4). Notice the larger capacitance developed by the GMOH electrode as compared to the MON and PEMO electrodes.

4.4. Evaluation of the performance of GMOH-GMOH symmetric supercapacitors

Next, the performance of the GMOH was evaluated further by assembling GMOH-GMOH symmetric supercapacitors and testing them in $0.5\text{ M K}_2\text{SO}_4$. Figure 6a shows representative cyclic voltammograms that displayed the rectangular-like shape typical of pseudocapacitive activity where a resistive behavior was significant only at scan rates as high as 500 mV s^{-1} . Galvanostatic charge-discharge experiments were carried out to evaluate capacitance, energy and power per unit volume and mass according to the Equations S1 to S3 (ESI) and the obtained values are summarized in Table 3. Figures 6b and 6c shows representative galvanostatic charge-discharge curves. Notice that a large current range of 0.25 to 10 A g^{-1} was considered. The charge-discharge curves showed a voltage drop due to ESR of 0.03 to 0.13 V . Figure 6d shows the capacitance per unit volume and mass as a function of applied current. The GMOH-GMOH symmetric supercapacitor achieved maximum capacitances of 40.9 F cm^{-3} and 73.5 F g^{-1} .

Figure 6 - Charge storage properties of the GMOH symmetric supercapacitor: (a) Representative cyclic voltammograms at various scan rates, (b), (c) galvanostatic charge-discharge curves at various testing currents, (d) capacitance per unit volume and per unit mass as function of testing currents (per unit area and mass) in galvanostatic charge-discharge experiments (e), (f) Ragone plots calculated per unit volume, and per unit mass, respectively, using galvanostatic charge-discharge experiments and (g) volumetric and gravimetric capacitance, calculated using galvanostatic charge-discharge experiments at a current of 3 A g^{-1} , as function of cycle number.

Figure 6e shows a Ragone plot per unit volume of the GMOH-GMOH symmetric supercapacitor along with previously reported data corresponding to devices/materials proposed for use as micro-supercapacitors and a thin film battery. The maximum energy and power per unit volume achieved were 5.5 mWh cm^{-3} and $2193.1 \text{ Wh cm}^{-3}$. Figure 6f shows a Ragone plot per unit mass of the GMOH-GMOH symmetric supercapacitor along with data corresponding to other manganese oxide-based symmetric supercapacitors. The maximum energy and power per unit mass achieved were 9.9 Wh kg^{-1} and 2506.3 W kg^{-1} . Figure 6g shows that the GMOH-GMOH symmetric supercapacitor had a capacitance retention of 55.0 % after 3,000 cycles. According to the operational requirements of a supercapacitor ($> 100,000$ cycles), this cyclability is poor. Notice that in this work, the set-up is not optimized for cycling stability. We exclude the use of polymeric binders which substantially improve cycling stability but decrease gravimetric capacitance. Previous work reports excellent cycling stability for an activated carbon- MnO_2 hybrid set-up where operational conditions, electrode manufacture and cell assembly have been set for an

optimum cycling stability [45]. This suggest that the cycling stability of our material can be further improved if similar testing conditions would be utilized.

Table 3 - Energy and power per unit volume and mass of GMOH-GMOH a symmetric supercapacitor

	Current 1 (A g⁻¹) 0.25	Current 2 10
Capacitance per volume (F cm⁻³)	40.9	16.0
Energy per volume (mWh cm⁻³)	5.5	2.2
Power per volume (mW cm⁻³)	34.2	2,193.1
Capacitance per mass (F g⁻¹)	73.5	18.2
Energy per mass (Wh kg⁻¹)	9.9	2.5
Power per mass (W kg⁻¹)	60.5	2,506.3

4.5. Comparison of the performance of the GMOH-based electrodes/ symmetric supercapacitor versus other electrodes/devices

Comparison of performance across devices must take into account a large number of variables including device configuration (half-cell, full-cell, interdigitated micro-supercapacitor [IM]), electrolytes used, weight and size of the device (footprint area, thickness, volume), and testing techniques (cyclic voltammetry, galvanostatic charge-discharge technique). Doing so can be a cumbersome task; nevertheless, we have attempted to provide some figures that help to place in context the performance of the GMOH- based electrodes/symmetric supercapacitor.

Table S3 (ESI) lists the gravimetric capacitance of GMOH electrodes/symmetric supercapacitor along with data corresponding to other manganese oxide-based electrodes/devices. The GMOH exhibited gravimetric capacitances of 217 F g⁻¹ (304 nm thick electrode, at 250 mA g⁻¹, half cell) and 73.5 F g⁻¹ (430 nm thick device, at 250 mA g⁻¹, full cell). This is larger than the gravimetric capacitance of other MnO₂ /GOG electrodes previously reported: needle-like MnO₂ onto GOG (197 F g⁻¹ at 250 mA g⁻¹, half-cell) [12] and MnO₂ nanosheets mixed with GOG (188 F g⁻¹ at 250 mA g⁻¹, half cell) [13]. Other works listed on Table S6 are not directly comparable with our work due to the use of asymmetric set-ups (a larger electrochemical window) [11,14] and the use of much lower testing currents [11]. As outlined above, using exfoliated graphene rather than “graphene” derived from graphene oxide has clear advantages in terms of better electrical conductivity, environmentally friendly nature (no toxic chemicals used), shorter production time scales (single-step and facile method), and by far, better cost-effectiveness (no need for hydrothermal, chemical or

physical processes for reduction that need special atmospheres) and scope for scalability [46].

Table S4 (ESI) lists the capacitance per unit area and volume of GMOH electrodes/symmetric supercapacitor along with data corresponding to some materials proposed for micro-supercapacitor applications. The device configurations include half-cells, full cells and IMs. The GMOH exhibited volumetric capacitances of 300 F cm^{-3} (69 nm thick electrode, CV at 5 mV s^{-1} , half cell), 82.5 F cm^{-3} (9.7 m thick electrode, CV at 5 mV s^{-1} , half cell) and 40.9 F cm^{-3} (430 nm thick device, at 250 mA g^{-1} equivalent to 3.4 A cm^{-2} , full cell). The GMOH exhibited a capacitance per unit area (geometric) of 80 mF cm^{-2} (9.7 m thick electrode, CV at 5 mV s^{-1} , half cell). A comparison of capacitance per unit area or volume is suitable only under the same electrode thickness and the same device configuration. Also, comparison is suitable only across materials undergoing similar energy storage processes. In the case of GMOH, a combination of double layer and pseudocapacitive energy storage processes. Looking at pseudocapacitive materials tested in half-cell set ups in Table S7, we have: titanium carbide $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ (340 F cm^{-3} , 2-20 m thick electrode, at 1 A g^{-1} , 1 M KOH, similar to the half-cell GMOH volumetric capacitance but not directly comparable due to the use of a different electrolyte and thicker electrodes) [47], titanium carbide $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ (80 F g^{-1} , 75-100 m thick electrode, CV at 2 mV s^{-1} , 0.5 M K_2SO_4 , smaller than the half-cell GMOH gravimetric capacitance of 217 F g^{-1} but not directly comparable due to the use of thicker electrodes) [47]. Looking at pseudocapacitive materials tested in full-cell set ups in Table S7, we have: VN-NiO (26.5 F cm^{-3} , 650 nm, asymmetric full cell, much lower than the volumetric capacitance of the GMOH symmetric supercapacitor of 40.9 F cm^{-3}) [48], VS_2 (317 F cm^{-3} , 150 nm, IM, larger than the volumetric capacitance of the GMOH symmetric supercapacitor of 40.9 F cm^{-3} but not directly comparable due to the use of a solid state electrolyte) [49], MoS_2 (178 F cm^{-3} , 450 nm, IM, larger than the volumetric capacitance of the GMOH symmetric supercapacitor of 40.9 F cm^{-3}) [50]. It is worth noticing that several devices here cited for comparison are IMs, which implies an improvement of performance due solely to electrode design and not necessarily associated with a superior electrochemical performance of the active materials. Therefore, their performance is not directly comparable to our full-cell GMOH supercapacitor in a “sandwich” configuration. The manufacture of IMs with GMOH is surely a further step of device improvement that will be addressed in future work.

Table S5 (ESI) lists the energy and power per unit area and volume of the GMOH symmetric supercapacitor along with data corresponding to some materials proposed for micro-supercapacitor applications and a thin film battery. The GMOH symmetric

supercapacitor achieved a volumetric energy of 5.5 mWh cm⁻³ at 34.2 mW cm⁻³ and 2.2 mWh cm⁻³ at 2.2 W cm⁻³. As shown in the Ragone plot in Figure 6d, this performance is superior to the performance of titanium carbide Ti₃C₂T_x (1 to 0.3 mWh cm⁻³ at a power of 0.01 to 0.18 W cm⁻³, full cell, 0.5 M K₂SO₄) [47]. As compared to the GMOH symmetric supercapacitor, a 25 mF supercapacitor exhibited an inferior volumetric energy but better volumetric power (0.3 to 0.1 mWh cm⁻³ at 0.60 to 10 W cm⁻³) [51]. The same can be said about carbon onions (1.5 to 0.5 mWh cm⁻³, full cell) [51]. A thin film battery exhibited superior volumetric energy than the GMOH symmetric supercapacitor but inferior volumetric power (8.5 to 0.4 mWh cm⁻³ at 1.5 to 5.5 mWh cm⁻³) [51]. As described in Table S8, all these electrodes/devices have different thicknesses, and thus the conclusions drawn above may or may not hold if the devices had the same thicknesses (not always explicit in the literature).

Table S6 (ESI) lists the energy and power per unit mass of the GMOH symmetric supercapacitor along with data corresponding to manganese oxide-based symmetric devices proposed for use as super- or micro-supercapacitors. The GMOH symmetric supercapacitor exhibited a energy density of 9.9 Wh kg⁻¹ at 60.5 W kg⁻¹ and 2.5 Wh kg⁻¹ at 2506.3 W kg⁻¹. As shown in Figure 6e, this performance is well in the range various other manganese-oxide based symmetric devices [52–56].

Despite the great variety of testing conditions which render any comparison ambiguous, we can say that the GMOH electrodes and the GMOH symmetric device have a competitive performance in terms of capacitance, energy and power per unit mass and volume and that offers potential for application in micro-supercapacitors.

5. Conclusions

In this study, we have developed a method of preparing hybrid dispersions made of nanosized 2D-nanosheets of graphene and manganese oxide following a simple, scalable and environmentally friendly liquid-phase co-exfoliation method. Binder free supercapacitor electrodes were then manufactured using a scalable spray deposition method. Graphene sheets were interleaved between the manganese oxide nanosheets producing a synergistic effect resulting in improved geometric, gravimetric and volumetric capacitances and improved energy and power performance per unit volume and mass. The presence of graphene in the hybrid was key for the achievement of an improved specific power and reduced electrical resistance. Raman spectroscopy, TGA and EIS studies confirmed the effective incorporation of graphene between the manganese oxide nanosheets. This effectively resulted in the reduction of the charge transfer resistance from

195.2 Ω for electrodes based solely on manganese oxide nanosheets to 4.3 Ω for the graphene-manganese oxide hybrid electrode.

The graphene-manganese oxide hybrid exhibited: a high geometric capacitance of 80 mF cm⁻² (for a 9.7 μ m thick electrode), a high volumetric capacitance of 300 F cm⁻³ (for a 69 nm thick electrode), 82.5 F cm⁻³ (for a 9.7 μ m thick electrode) and 40.9 F cm⁻³ (for a symmetric device), a gravimetric capacitance of 217 F g⁻¹ (for a single electrode) and 73.5 F g⁻¹ (for a symmetric device), maximum energy and power per unit volume of 5.5 mWh cm⁻³ and 2,193.1 mW cm⁻³ (for a symmetric device), and maximum energy and power per unit mass of 9.9 Wh kg⁻¹ and 2,506.3 W kg⁻¹ (for a symmetric device). Such performance is competitive with previously reported materials and devices proposed for supercapacitor applications. Specifically, the GMOH is a suitable candidate for micro-supercapacitor applications.

The successful improvement of charge storage properties by combining 2D nanomaterials in a hybrid demonstrates the potential and remarkable versatility of our methodology (based on liquid-phase co-exfoliation and spray deposition) to develop other hybrid systems. New venues of research are open, and future work will be dedicated to the development of novel hybrid electrodes of 2D nanomaterials with enhanced properties.

Electronic Supplementary Information

Details about electrode manufacture, equipment and characterization techniques; Further TEM analysis; Rietveld analysis of MOFN, MON and PEMO; TGA data and nitrogen adsorption isotherms of MOFN, MON and GMOH; galvanostatic charge discharge curves and corresponding parameters summarized in tables; EIS spectra and details of the EEC used to fit the EIS data along with a table summarizing the determined EEC parameters; and comparative tables of the performance of GMOH electrodes versus other electrodes/devices previously reported.

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